

Simulating the Acoustic Environment of Two Historical Viennese Theaters

Brandon Westergaard

Center for Music Technology, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, Georgia, USA

brandon.westergaard@gatech.edu

Timothy Hsu

timothy.hsu@music.gatech.edu

ABSTRACT

Historic performance spaces throughout the world have stood the test of time, in many cases reportedly due to their superior acoustics. Numerous studies focus on measurements made within these spaces to verify or disprove these claims. Regardless of the reason for their demise, the reputations of a number of historic theaters have been maintained due to the significance of their performances and premieres. Not all these spaces remain in the present day for modern study and analysis; however, current computational technologies allow extinct theaters to be digitally reconstructed and simulated. This work focuses on the construction of models and acoustic simulations for two notable Viennese theaters from the 18th century. Analysis elucidates how room acoustics may have been perceived within the spaces during a period when opera and theater were thriving in the region. Moreover, the acoustic characteristics of these theaters are compared to the standards of modern metrics. In doing so, a determination of the quality of each venue is made.

1. INTRODUCTION

Music was an essential part of Viennese life at the turn of the 18th century [1]. The city was prosperous at the time, and the theater had become the top ranked entertainment among the public [2]. Vienna's prosperity made music and theater accessible to even the common person. Thus, the theater's importance extended beyond mere entertainment, serving to unite members of every class [1].

Of particular importance during this time were the Old Burgtheater and the Freihaus Theater auf der Wieden, a court theater and private suburban theater, respectively. Both theaters presumably had desirable acoustics because of their construction materials [1,3]. Likewise, each theater was well-equipped for theatrics from a technical standpoint [4]. Beyond spoken drama, the environment inside these two houses may have been suitable for opera. Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart premiered operas of historical importance at both these theaters during his time in Vienna.

In providing an overview of the acoustic environment of these theaters, a particular challenge is encountered: neither theater stands during the present day. As such, past accounts of the quality of the sound field in the auditoriums are purely anecdotal [5]. However, modern computing affords the opportunity to recreate the architectural structures of the interiors. In doing so, acoustic simula-

tion software packages can be used to map modern metrics to audience surfaces as well as to auralize the sound field within the theaters. This paper provides a quantitative evaluation of each theater's performance based on the results of simulated models. Such evaluations provide insight into the theaters' abilities to house opera and allow estimations and opinions of the theaters' acoustics to be verified.

2. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

In order to analyze and discuss the comparative acoustics of the Old Burgtheater and the Freihaus Theater auf der Wieden in a similar historical context, the theaters should be contemporaries of one another. Both theaters had a relatively limited lifespan; however, there does exist a time period in which both theaters were simultaneously operating. This time period coincides with Mozart's time in Vienna, from 1781 until his death in 1791 [6]. Mozart composed in Vienna during the Enlightenment, corresponding with the reign of Emperor Joseph II, who took over the Viennese throne in 1776 [2]. This same year, Joseph created the German National Theater in the Burgtheater, making it a court theater dedicated to German drama [7]. By this time, the theater had undergone renovations to improve the visual affinity and listening environment of the auditorium.

A humble beginning, the Burgtheater was constructed in 1741 from a wooden structure that housed tennis courts, as seen in drawings by Friedrich Wilhelm Weiskern [8]. However, the theater was completely remodeled after a new design by architect Nicholas Jadot, adding a proper proscenium, noble loges, a number of decorative elements, and an extension of the stage house. The stage house was further extended in 1759 [8]. The model created for this study matches the structure of the Burgtheater after a 1779 renovation completed by architect Franz Anton Hillebrandt. During this iteration, tiers of boxes were added next to the stage [8]. In this form, the Burgtheater staged three Mozart opera premieres, including *The Abduction from the Seraglio*, the most successful German opera to arise from Joseph's establishment of the German National Theater [9]. Following another minor renovation in 1794, the Burgtheater interior construction remained constant until the theater was demolished in 1888.

The Freihaus Theater auf der Wieden was built in 1787 by Christian Rossbach, based on drawings by the district architect, Andreas Zach. Another reform from the emperor, the Schauspielfreiheit, relaxed theater licensing laws and allowed for suburban theaters like the Freihaus Thea-

ter to flourish [2]. This reform also initiated the revival of German opera in the Freihaus, as the Burgtheater had transitioned to Italian opera in 1783 [7]. Emmanuel Schikaneder took over the operation of the Freihaus Theater in July of 1789 after the death of its original director [1]. Schikaneder was a theater man known for grand theatrical spectacles during performance; thus, leading to the general popularity of Schikaneder's company and theater [1,2,10]. For the majority of its lifetime, the Freihaus Theater operated independently, as Schikaneder's company had its own composers, librettists, singers, and musicians [11]. However, Schikaneder's collaboration with Mozart on *The Magic Flute*, which premiered on September 30, 1791, was a major exception [10]. The opera was performed 223 times, cementing a historical legacy for the Freihaus Theater. The theater was replaced by Schikaneder's Theater an der Wien in 1801 [10].

Figure 1. Burgtheater floor plan at ground level, Joseph Hillebrandt (1779) [12]

Although limited, historical documents and evidence still remain for both theaters which aid in the construction of an interior architectural model [2,8,10]. Regarding the Burgtheater, these documents indicate that the interior of the theater consisted almost entirely of wood paneling. Additionally, along the backstage wall, the theater had three large, high bay windows; however, they were likely obscured for many performances. Its circular staircases in the rear corners were made of stone. Its boxes, including the large “Gallerie noble” at its rear, were carpeted in red. The seats and benches in the theater were upholstered and cushioned, making them more absorptive. Its suggested capacity is approximately 1,350 people. Using the Sabine formula, Herta Singer estimated that the Burgtheater had a reverberation time between 1 and 1.3 seconds, depending on the size of the audience [3]. The general shape of the theater and the location of its parterre are shown in Figure 1—taken from the 1779 floor plan drawn by Joseph Hillebrandt [12]. A companion floor plan also exists (not pictured), showing the first level and a clearer configuration of the boxes. These are the floor plans on which the model of the Burgtheater is based.

The Freihaus Theater shares many of the interior characteristics of the Burgtheater, including its building materials and seating configuration. *Opera in Context* refers to the theater as “a substantial structure of brick and stone, with a tile roof and interior of wood paneling” [2]. Besides the stage and proscenium, the theater consisted of a parterre, a parterre noble, a noble gallery, and a sec-

ond gallery. An assortment of upholstered and unupholstered benches were located throughout the parterre and galleries, the details of which are listed in [13]. The theater housed around 800 audience members and 40 musicians in the orchestra pit. Unfortunately, a reverberation study similar to Singer's is not known to exist. The present Freihaus model is modeled after the Andreas Zach floor plan, shown below in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Freihaus Theater floor plan at lower level (top) and upper level (bottom), Andreas Zach (1789) [5]

3. ACOUSTIC BACKGROUND

The following section presents a brief description of the acoustic metrics used and how they may apply to opera.

3.1 Acoustic Metrics

Reverberation time (RT) is the time it takes for a sound to decay by 60 dB [14]. To the listener, it is the time in which a sound in a space becomes inaudible. The present acoustic models make available the Eyring and Sabine formulas for calculating RT. In addition, the Schroeder RT can be obtained from simulation, discussed in Section 4. While the Sabine and Eyring RT can be calculated solely from the amount of absorption within a given volume, the Schroeder RT must be measured, either on site or within a computer model.

Similar to reverberation time, early decay time (EDT) is the time it takes for a musical tone to decay by 10 dB, multiplied by a factor of 6 [14]. EDT can be considered a perceptual indicator of reverberation time, as an audience will likely only hear the first fragment of decay during a fast passage of notes. If early energy decays more rapidly than later energy (i.e. $EDT < RT$), successive syllables and notes are less likely to be masked. In this way, EDT exhibits a relationship with clarity.

Clarity refers to the level at which a listener can distinguish individual sounds during a performance [14]. It is expressed in positive or negative dB, the former meaning a predominance of early sound energy at the listener position and the latter indicating higher reverberant sound energy. C_{80} is specifically used for music, a ratio of ener-

gy arriving at the listener position during the first 80 ms and the remaining sound energy after 80 ms.

Speech intelligibility is a measure of how well speech can be understood within a given environment. Here, Sound Transmission Index (STI) is used to gauge speech intelligibility. This metric uses the Modulation Transfer Function (MTF), a filter characteristic applied to the input signal within a specific enclosure, to calculate its single number value [15].

3.2 Opera Acoustics

Opera has the distinct characteristic of combining instrumental music with sung passages that highlight a libretto meant to be understood. Therefore, opera houses should have a relatively low reverberation time, somewhere between 1.4 and 1.6 seconds [16]. An audience contributes a fair amount of absorptive material, helping to reduce reverberation time during a performance [17]. EDT may be a better indicator of acoustical quality of opera houses, especially when considering a Mozart opera and its fast tempo arias and melismas. Additionally, adequate clarity must be present throughout the opera house. A positive C_{80} quantity is desirable for opera, somewhere between 1 and 3 dB [16], ensuring that lyrical passages can be heard and understood. Clarity decreases as distance from the source increases, making the forward seats within an opera house preferable [18]. Mozart himself noticed this. After listening to a performance of *The Magic Flute*, he stated, “You have no idea how charming the music sounds when you hear it from a box close to the orchestra—it sounds much better than from the gallery” [2]. Per IEC 60268-16:2011, speech intelligibility is considered unacceptable for STI values between 0 and 0.3, poor from 0.3 to 0.45, fair from 0.45 to 0.6, good from 0.6 to 0.75, and excellent from 0.75 to 1 [19]. The libretto and score share equal importance in an opera performance. Therefore, an ideal opera house should have an STI value above 0.6, within the good or excellent range.

Certain acoustic characteristics of theater boxes, or opera house boxes, pertain to the present study. In many opera houses, the acoustics inside a box are poor [17]. This is due to the size of the opening; if the opening is too small for the box to behave as an acoustically coupled room, it is effectively separate from the main volume of the room. Thus, much of the incident sound is reflected back to the stalls [18]. The presence of boxes affects sound distribution differently across the frequency spectrum. They act as resonators in the low frequencies and traps in the high frequencies [18]. Additionally, sound absorptive materials appear in boxes, causing a decrease in perceived volume. Usually, boxes are only acoustically preferable at the very front toward the opening because clarity decreases farther into the box.

4. COMPUTER SIMULATION METRICS

The Enhanced Acoustic Simulator for Engineers (EASE) software by the Ahnert Feistel Media Group (AFMG) was used for simulating the sound field within each theater. Specifically, the program's AURA algorithm was utilized to obtain the room responses and perform aurali-

zations [20]. AURA employs a hybrid model that uses an image source model for early reflections and ray-tracing for modeling energy of late and scattered reflections. For a given source-receiver configuration, AURA traces sound rays emitted from a source through a room until they impact a “balloon” centered at head height of the receiver position. The collection of rays is used to build a reflectogram, a collection of impacts recorded at a particular location over time, showing the energy of each impact. The energy contained within the reflectogram can be backward integrated to obtain the Schroeder curve, from which the reverberation time can be determined at a specific receiver location [21].

AURA generates the reflectogram to obtain the binaural impulse at a specific receiver location. Convolution of this impulse response with an anechoic recording yields an auralization of the simulated space. Kleiner gives a detailed overview of the auralization process in [22].

5. METHODOLOGY

Opera in Context compiles a list of theater dimensions from known historical studies; however, each scholar's interpretation of the architectural drawings is understandably different. These differences are partially due to general methodology or specific measurement decisions, such as conversion errors from an extinct unit of measurement, the Austrian *Klafter* (seen in Figure 2) [2]. Similarly, it is unclear whether each scholar interpreted auditorium width as wall-to-wall width or loge-to-loge width.

To overcome the dimension challenge, new drawing measurements and conversions were undertaken using digital markup tools in Bluebeam Revu. The *Klafter* scale provided a reference for the Freihaus Theater, with one *Klafter* set equal to 1.89 meters [23]. For the Burgtheater, the width of the proscenium arch served as the common reference, as this dimension is generally agreed upon in the historical studies. Auditorium width was interpreted as the wall-to wall width. Table 1 provides the measured dimensions for the Burgtheater and Freihaus Theater.

	Burgtheater	Freihaus Theater
Total Length	145.5 ft	118 ft
Auditorium Length	72 ft	45.5 ft
Auditorium Width	49 ft	49 ft
Height	43 ft	24.5 ft
Stage Length	73.5 ft	43.5 ft
Stage Width	42 – 56 ft	49 ft
Stage Height	5 ft	5 ft
Proscenium Width	30 ft	33 ft
Proscenium Height	30 ft	13 ft
Pit Depth	8.5 ft	7.5 ft
Total Volume	268,546 ft ³	103,037 ft ³

Table 1. Burgtheater and Freihaus Theater dimensions

Architectural models for both theaters were constructed in Trimble's SketchUp, a 3D modeling software. Knowledge of performance staging informed the modeled stage length of the Burgtheater. The length of stage utilized varied between performances, often shortened to obscure the back wall's windows and include the appro-

priate backdrop. The stage length was shortened accordingly to 40 feet, resulting in a new total volume of 214,850 ft³. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show views of the Burgtheater and Freihaus Theater models from the stage.

Figure 3. Burgtheater model, view from stage

Figure 4. Freihaus theater model, view from stage

Upon importing a model into EASE, audience areas were placed and assigned the absorption coefficients of an audience in the appropriate seating (upholstered, un-upholstered, standing), giving the absorptive characteristic of an actual audience. Audience areas appear at ear height. Seven audience areas added to the Burgtheater model covered both parterre, a box at each level, and the noble gallery. Listener seats (i.e. receiver locations) added to each area provided locations for detailed analysis and auralization. Twenty-seven audience areas were added to the Freihaus Theater model, including both parterre, all boxes, and both galleries. In addition, a number of receiver locations were added throughout the audience areas, four of which were used to make auralizations. Omnidirectional spherical sources were located five feet downstage and center-stage within each model. Figure 5 and Figure 6 show views of each model in plan. Green polygons represent audience areas, blue horns represent source locations, and red squares represent receiver locations.

Figure 5. Burgtheater acoustic model with appropriate stage length, plan view

Figure 6. Freihaus Theater acoustic model, plan view

An average of one and a quarter million rays were used for calculations within the AURA module in order to ensure high impact probability at the receiver, resulting in high resolution mappings and reflectograms. The length of the simulations was set equal to the product of the mean free path time and the maximum reflection order, with a broadband scattering effect of 20%. Section 6 shows the results of the simulations, including Schroeder RT's and the acoustic metrics outlined in Section 3. Auralizations were created at specified listener seats by convolving the binaural impulse response at the receiver with an anechoic recording of Donna Elvira's aria from Mozart's opera, *Don Giovanni*. Receiver locations include the center of the noble parterre, center of the top balcony, and a box closest to the stage on the right.

6. RESULTS

6.1 Burgtheater

Figure 7 shows a plot of the Sabine RT and Schroeder RT taken from the Burgtheater EASE simulation. The Sabine RT increases from 0.63 s in the lowest one-third octave band to 1.43 s at 1000 Hz, at which it begins to steadily fall off. The Schroeder RT spans a similar range, increasing from 0.91 s in the lowest one-third octave band to 1.87 s at 1000 Hz, then decreasing with increasing frequency above 1000 Hz. The mid-frequency reverberation time RT_{mid} , the reverberation time averaged over the 500 and 1000 Hz octave bands, is 1.18 s, using the Sabine formula. The Schroeder RT_{mid} was calculated at 1.53 s.

Figure 7. Burgtheater Reverberation Time, 1/3 octave band. Sabine RT: solid black line; Schroeder RT: dashed line; EDT: solid gray line.

Early Decay Time in the Burgtheater shares the general contour of the RT curve, also shown in Figure 7. However, the values across all octave bands are higher than Sabine and Schroeder RT. EDT reaches its peak at 1000 Hz at 2.02 s. The mid-frequency average EDT was calculated at 1.68 s at the center of the stalls. Clarity (C_{80}) fluctuated from 3 dB in the front boxes to -0.75 dB in the rear boxes. C_{80} values hover just above 0 dB throughout most of the theater. Over much of the stalls, C_{80} is 0 dB, an equal balance of direct and reverberant sound. C_{80} was near 0.15 dB inside the noble gallery and 0.85 dB on the top gallery. The Speech Transmission Index (STI) spanned from 0.46 to 0.62 throughout the theater. Its lowest value appeared throughout the rear boxes and over the rear parterre. Peak STI occurred in the forward boxes. The galleries showed an STI slightly higher than 0.5.

6.2 Freihaus Theater

Figure 8 shows a plot of the Sabine RT and Schroeder RT for the Freihaus Theater. The shape of the curves is similar to the Burgtheater's due to similar interior construction materials. However, the values are slightly lower as expected in a smaller theater. The Sabine RT increases from 0.59 s in the lowest one-third octave band to 1.17 s at 1000 Hz, falling off thereafter. The Schroeder RT increases from 0.8 s in the lowest one-third octave band to 1.78 s at 1000 Hz, again decreasing thereafter. The Sabine RT_{mid} is 1.0 s, and the Schroeder RT_{mid} is 1.48 s.

Early Decay Time in the Freihaus Theater also shares the general contour of the RT curve, shown in Figure 8. The values are similar to the Schroeder RT across the frequency spectrum. EDT reaches its peak at 1000 Hz, at 1.88 s. At the center of the main floor (towards the front of the rear parterre), the mid-frequency average EDT was calculated at 1.52 s. Clarity (C_{80}) fluctuated from 4 dB in the front boxes to 1.5 dB in the rear boxes. C_{80} was near 1 dB on the galleries, approaching 0 dB in areas of the upper balcony. The Speech Transmission Index spanned from 0.5 to 0.67 throughout the theater. It remained near 0.55 over most of the main floor and in the rear boxes. Peak STI occurred in the first two boxes, whereas the lowest values appeared on the sides of the galleries.

Table 2 and Table 3 summarize the data obtained from the simulations.

Figure 8. Freihaus Theater Reverberation Time, 1/3 octave band. Sabine RT: solid black line; Schroeder RT: dashed line; EDT: solid gray line.

	Burgtheater	Freihaus Theater
Sabine RT_{mid}	1.18 s	1.0 s
Schroeder RT_{mid}	1.53 s	1.48 s
EDT _{mid}	1.68 s	1.52 s
STI _{max}	0.60	0.65

Table 2. Summary of simulated data

	Burgtheater	Freihaus Theater
Forward Boxes	3 dB	4 dB
Rear Boxes	-0.75 dB	1.4 dB
Galleries	0.85 dB	1.0 dB
Stalls	0 dB	2 dB
Noble Gallery	0.15 dB	-

Table 3. Clarity (C_{80}) by location

7. DISCUSSION

The respective ranges of the reverberation time metrics for the Burgtheater and Freihaus Theater are reasonable, based on the physical characteristics of each space. Excessive reverberation was not expected in either theater, given their relatively low volumes. The reverberation time plots, Figure 7 and Figure 8, show a similar trend at frequencies below 1000 Hz. In this band, reverberation time decreases with decreasing frequency, as expected given the construction materials. For both theaters, the interior surface area is dominated by wood paneling or flooring, at 89.7% in the Burgtheater and 91.9% in the Freihaus Theater, leading to higher absorption coefficients in the lower octave bands. The audience did not significantly affect the shape of the RT curve. However, there was an average reduction in reverberation time by 0.37 s due to the presence of an audience.

Based on volume alone, the Freihaus Theater was expected to have a significantly lower reverberation time. However, the Schroeder RT's differ by less than a tenth of a second due to presence of more elaborate seating, larger audiences, and carpeted boxes in the Burgtheater. The stage house of the Freihaus Theater may also affect the liveness of the auditorium, contributing a longer re-

verberation tail. Both theaters would have seemed significantly drier than the famous concert halls for which Vienna is known. For example, their reverberation time is a half second shorter than that of the Musikverein, which opened three decades before the demolition of the old Burgtheater [14]. Of course, the theaters, functioning as opera houses, should be drier to ensure the vocalists are understood. Although of a different era, the reconstructed modern Vienna Staatsoper could have rivaled these fallen theaters. Although the Staatsoper is larger, it is fairly dry, with a RT_{mid} of 1.3 s and adequate clarity [14]. The former theaters both seated a large audience for their size, which contributed to seemingly cramped quarters.

While the shape of the RT curve indicates a poor bass ratio, the reverberant field in each was ideal. In order to clearly hear the articulations and intricacies of opera music, the materials should absorb lower frequencies and reflect high frequencies [17]. The wood paneling of both theaters gives this effect. Furthermore, the Schroeder reverberation times for both theaters fall within the ideal range that Hidaka and Beranek define. The Sabine RT calculated for the model aligns with Singer's Sabine estimate, providing indication of the simulation's validity.

EDT provides an indication of how patrons perceived the reverberant field in each theater. In both cases, the EDT curve exceeds the Sabine and Schroeder RT, indicating that the theaters may have seemed more reverberant than their size suggested. The auralizations further verify this result. Although a live environment could have complemented passages at slower tempos, early sound energy may not have decayed rapidly enough to permit intelligibility of typical 18th century coloratura style. It is also important to consider the modern reverberation time standards as a measure of quality. The EDT of the Freihaus Theater ranges from 1.4 to 1.6s, and the Burgtheater exceeds the desirable range by just a tenth of a second.

Reflected sound is more predominant in the Burgtheater than the Freihaus Theater; C_{80} values are lower throughout the theater. As expected, reflected sound energy exceeds direct sound energy as one moves further back in a box. Notably, strong early reflections are received on the upper galleries as is evident in the auralizations. As these seats were inexpensive, audience members in these areas may have had an acceptable experience at a bargain. Through much of the theater, clarity is just short of the desired lower limit, causing potentially "muddy" sounds. The Freihaus Theater exhibited a similar clarity distribution over various locations. However, its C_{80} values were higher, falling into a desirable range at all sampled receiver locations. Again, a strong presence of vocals can be heard from the top balcony, even more so than in the stalls. In both theaters, Mozart's quotation holds true; the boxes closest to the stage were the best seats in the house.

Speech intelligibility is acceptable through both theaters, degrading as expected as the receiver location moves further away from the source. However, it was not exceptional, only exceeding a value of 0.6 within small regions close to the stage. A performer would need to consider this factor, actively projecting to be entirely understood.

The two Viennese theaters modeled and simulated for the present study represent only a small part of historically significant, non-extant theaters for which architectural

data is available. The present study could therefore be extended in a number of directions. First, expansion over a more geographically diverse area within the same time period could lead to meaningful comparisons between regions. Conversely, ongoing work could focus on simulating theaters chronologically in time. In this scenario, the next logical step is modeling the historic Theater on der Wien, considered the successor to the Freihaus Theater. Both directions offer the opportunity to study the correlation between composition style and acoustics of historical halls. In this vein, it may also be useful to consider multi-source auralizations, where individual instruments and vocalists could be modeled as separate sources within a hall. Doing so could provide an accurate spatial recreation of a performance. Recreation of historic halls ties into historical musicology as well, providing a basis for studying the context surrounding a composer's compositions. Likely, room acoustics of a particular venue influenced the compositional style of composers within a region or time period, similar to how they might compose for a specific vocalist.

8. CONCLUSION

The theater was an instrumental part of Viennese lifestyle, aiming to educate and entertain the public. In late 18th century Vienna, German theater thrived in the court theater, the Burgtheater. After licensing laws relaxed, suburban theaters like the Freihaus prospered as well. Neither the Burgtheater nor the Freihaus Theater were built solely for opera; however, acoustic simulation indicates that each was suitable for opera. Both featured interiors of wood paneling, material contributing to bright sound field. The audience, especially elaborately dressed, lowered reverberation time during performances.

Both theaters compare favorably to modern standards. The reverberation times fall within the standard for opera. Audiences would have clearly heard the articulations of vocalists and a full bodied instrumental sound. Even those in the cheap seats of the upper galleries received strong reflections, contributing to a sense of envelopment. Reflected sound would have been more noticeable in the Burgtheater due to the auditorium's clarity, but direct sound energy was still dominant in most seating areas. Especially given its small size, clear musical details would have projected throughout the Freihaus Theater. Sitting in a forward box was likely not ideal from a visual standpoint but would have been a pleasure to experience from an aural standpoint.

The opportunity to measure the Burgtheater and Freihaus Theater was lost following each theater's demise. However, through careful study of the surviving floor plans, the structure can be erected in the digital domain. The proximity of Singer's estimated Sabine RT and the simulated Sabine RT strengthens the validity of simulations within the Burgtheater. It follows that similar modeling and simulation parameters yield a reliable result for the Freihaus Theater. While their historical significance is sealed by their catalog of important performances and premieres, the acoustics of these two Viennese theaters deserves recognition as well.

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